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Titel

Mobilization of phosphorus from secondary minerals by the arbuscular mycorrhiza *Rhizophagus irregularis* and consequences for carbon sequestration in soils

Abstract

Phosphorus can be a major limiting factor for plant growth due to its slow diffusion and high degree of immobilization in soils. Understanding the strategies evolved by plant-symbiont couples increasing P uptake is crucial, under the aim of adopting the involved mechanisms by modern sustainable agriculture. This study aims to explore whether tomato plants mycorrhized with the arbuscular mycorrhizal (AM) fungi *Rhizophagus irregularis* have the ability to mobilize P from secondary minerals and organic sources. Our hypothesis was that AM-bearing plants will invest more carbon to their fungal symbiont in case P must be exploited from less accessible P sources. For this, we carried out a time course experiment (91 days) with split-chamber mesocosms ensuring the mobilization of P by the mycorrhizal partner only. Orthophosphate (OP) and phytic acid (PA) in their free state and adsorbed to goethite (GOE-OP; GOE-PA) have been offered to the host plant. According to our knowledge, this is the first report where an organic P source bonded to a secondary mineral has been tested as a plant P source via the mycorrhizal P uptake pathway.

The PLFA 16:1 ω 5c is known to be part of the membrane constituents and it is considered a good AM biomass estimator (Olsson and Wilhelmsson 2000). In our study it correlated positively with incorporated P and the AM plant root activity (arbuscules %) for all provided P sources.

Additionally, those AM plants which accessed OP and GOE-OP also showed a positive significant correlation of the arbuscules percentages, with the incorporated P, the PLFA 18:1 ω 7c, and in case of GOE-PA also with the PLFA 18:2 ω 6,9. These two PLFA biomarkers have been previously found in *R. irregularis* hyphae (Olsson et al. 2002) and might indicate that AM fungi modified their fatty acid composition in the hyphae during the mobilization of P from the different P sources.

As fungal energy storage we also measured the NLFA 16:1 ω 5c. It was significantly higher for both P sources bonded to goethite compared to free OP and PA. These results point towards different C investment to uptake of P through the mycorrhizal pathway having a direct consequence for the carbon sequestration in soils.

Literatur

Olsson PA, Van Aarle IM, Allaway WG, et al (2002) Phosphorus Effects on Metabolic Processes in Monoxenic Arbuscular Mycorrhiza Cultures. *Plant Physiol* 130:1162-1171. doi: 10.1104/pp.009639.

Olsson PA, Wilhelmsson P (2000) The growth of external AM fungal mycelium in sand dunes and in experimental systems. *Plant Soil* 226:161-169. doi: 10.1023/A:1026565314345.